

A Study on Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel with Special Reference to Consumer at Tiruchirappalli City

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Abstract

A Study on the Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel With special reference to a consumer at Tiruchirappalli City.

Television Advertisement assumes a noteworthy job in present-day life. It shapes the states of mind of the general public and the individual and definitely impacts customer behavior. The customer needs to fight with a gigantic measure of data and have the capacity to settle on a decision, reach determinations and settle on critical choices. This examination plans to set up whether the Trichy City, Tamilnadu, customers affects their purchasing choices because of the impact of Apparel retailer's TV advertisements.

An advertisement is the paid type of unoriginal introduction of thoughts, products, and ventures by distinguished support. The primary goal of promoting is to advise, influence and remind the focused on shoppers with respect to the item. Consistently we go over an assortment of advertisements. When we read a daily paper or a magazine or tune in to the radio or stare at the television or stroll on a street or travel by a transport or a prepare or we see a film or go anyplace else, we run over a type of an advertisement. These advertisements fill in as the main thrust for our buy choices.

The main objective of this paper is to study on the Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel reference to a consumer at Tiruchirappalli City.

A descriptive study was done on primary data collected from 125 respondents on basis of judgmental sampling. 125 respondents were given questionnaire and 110 were found to be fully usable for analysis. A questionnaire was used to collect primary data. Likert five-point scaling was given to customers for evaluating their impact of Demographical factors on Apparel retail store selection. IBM SPSS Statistic version 20.0 was used for this analysis and the following tools were administered 1) Reliability Test 2) Factor Analysis and 3) Multiple Regression 4) Chi-square goodness of fit test. The reliability test was made and the obtained coefficient alpha value (Cronbach's alpha) was 0. 0.937, and hence the data had satisfactory reliability. Factor analysis and Multiple Regression was used to find the Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel.

In the Chi-square test, we are assessing how well the sample data fits the population proportions specified by the hypothesis.

Keywords: Television Advertisement, Awareness, Consumer Buying Behavior, Customer satisfaction, women apparels. Consumer decision making process.

Introduction

Advertising assumes an essential job in the general public, by and large, and in the business, specifically. It goes about as a system of offers advancement and innovation. Advertising is fundamental on account of inside and in addition worldwide promoting. In the meantime, it is important on account of a wide range of items - old, entrenched and new. The fundamental goals of advertising are to give data, to pull in consideration, to make mindfulness and to impact purchasing behavior of buyers.

Advertising is utilized for imparting, trading/ conveying business data to the present and imminent customers. It, for the most part, gives data about the advertising firm, its item characteristics, place of accessibility of its items, and so forth. An advertisement is crucial for both the merchants and the purchasers. Be that as it may, it is more vital for the vendors. In the cutting edge period of expansive scale creation, makers can't consider pushing offer of their items without advertising them. Advertisement supplements individual pitching as it were. Advertising has Procured incredible significance in the cutting edge world where intense rivalry in the market and quick changes in innovation.

In this advanced profoundly aggressive world, no producer can exceed expectations in his item conveyance except if he makes interest for the item. Advertising is a vital strategy for interest creation as it prompts huge scale offering. It has turned out to be essential that notwithstanding the business associations, instructive establishments, magnanimous organizations and government bodies are utilizing it.

David Potter's definition express that advertising is an administration foundation which makes individuals mindful of their needs and makes them cautious buyers. His definition is as per the following: "The main establishment we have for imparting new needs, for preparing individuals to go about as customers, for changing men's qualities and consequently to hurry their acclimation to potential plenitude is advertising".

The salient features of advertising are:

1. Advertising provides information,
2. Advertising is a paid form of communication,

3. Advertising is a nonpersonal presentation,
4. Advertising gives publicity to goods, services, and ideas,
5. Advertising is by an identified sponsor,
6. Advertising is for persuasion,
7. Advertising is target oriented,
8. Advertising is an art, science, and profession.
9. Advertising is an important element in the marketing mix, and
10. Creativity - the essence of advertising.

The Growth of Advertising is Presented in Chart Growth of Advertising

The impact of television is fundamental due to its colossal potential as a varying media communicator. Television (T.V.) empowers the innovative man to impart by consolidating movement, sounds, words, shading, identity and stage setting to express and exhibit thoughts to an extensive and generally dispersed group of onlookers. T.V. advertisements normally assume a job in either presenting an item strengthening the nature to the item and furthermore persuading to buy the item. Advertisements are among the most unmistakable of the promoting procedure and have been the subject of a lot of consideration in the last ten to fifteen years. Advertisement can't just change feelings yet give the subliminal message. Advertising today is by all accounts all over and ever-present applying an extensive impact on the day by day lives of individuals. Advertisements create self-ideas with the end goal to prompt buy choices. Television advertising utilizes eye-catching trap, for example, snappy and satisfying music, verses, Jingles, humor, and rehashed messages. The impact of the advertisements is more on television than the print media or radio.

Television commercials affect culture. Prior individuals used to live in an alternate way yet observing every one of these projects and advertisements individuals have changed their mentalities. Individuals have changed the manner in which they dress, their haircuts and states of mind.’

‘Everybody sees the advertisements on television and they can attempt to look out what is great from the advertisements. We can figure out what can be utilized for our improvement from advertisements. You can figure out how to act and act from such things.’

Consequently, television commercials were utilized to choose what items to purchase, as well as how to act. Individuals in even the remotest regions could perceive what was suitable and worthy. Subsequently, individuals were accepting a few angles, for example, dressing in a comparable way to individuals in the commercials, while likewise keeping up a few parts of Indian culture.

Women and Clothing

Clothing has seen an especially emotional change for some youthful center and wealthier class ladies. Youthful, autonomous, unmarried profession arranged ladies are as often as possible delineated on television and television commercials, wearing western-style clothing, for example, western dresses, skirts, salwars, pants etc.

Literature Review

Understanding the Consumers’ attitude towards advertisements assume significance as it reflects her attitude towards the advertised products also, to an extent. The attitude of consumers is generally influenced by the type of advertising exposure and the intensity of attention towards such advertisements. The need for investigating the attitude of consumers towards the TV. Internet advertisements are expressed in many national and international journals. With this notion, the researcher reviewed the literature related to attitude and are presented below.

Rana (1995) undertook a study on T.V. advertisements and expressed that among the media, the impact of television advertisement on social behavior, including purchasing behavior was the greatest. The reason is that television has charm, instantaneous transmission capability, and universality of appeal.

Heyam Ali, Rasha Saad, Ahmed Ahmed, BabikerEl- Haj (2015) examined the attitudes and behavior of emirates women related to facial skin care products. To discover the similarities and differences in the attitudes and behavior of young and middle-aged women when using these products and to discover what kind of attitudes of emirates women have towards facial skin care products containing natural ingredients. The results indicated that women in the two age categories were rather similar in terms of attitudes and behavior related to facial skin care products, however, some differences were also found for example in the decision –making process. Regarding the attitudes toward the use of natural ingredients in facial skin care products, differences were found between different demographic groups.

SueLin, C. (2010) Studied the role of emotions in advertisements, the factors that drive cosmetics consumption When the factors that drove and influenced consumer decisions presented in the consumer models were used to analyze the Japanese Cosmetics consumption, they revealed the prevalence of Maslow’s higher order needs such as self - esteem, sense of belonging and self - actualization in driving cosmetics consumption and brand choice.

Shimpi, S. S., & Sinha, D. K. (2010) Investigated and evaluated attitude characteristics which affects consumer buying behavior of male cosmetics products in Pune city. self-esteem, anxiety, and conformity have given more significance by Pune men for purchasing male cosmetics products.

The ORG Survey (2011) indicated that the major items which accounted for about 45-50 percent of the rural market were washing soaps, cleaning materials, toiletries, and food and beverage. But the survey also observed that the growth rate was very significant in certain items like cosmetics and toiletries over a period of five years.

Shukla Pritesh Kumar Y. (2013) concluded that television plays an important role to increase competitiveness in rural areas. It was found a majority of rural respondents are using television as their main source of information. It also strongly indicates that the rural respondents who use television as their main source of information would be definitely getting knowledge of other brands from the same source.

Lokesh Sharma, Archana Singh & Dr. Parul D. Agarwal (2014) revealed that adults strongly believe that TV advertisements have considerably influenced their buying process.

Ersoy, Nazi Figen; Yolal, Medet; Batmaz, Bulent (2015) examine the attitudes of Turkish men towards cosmetic consumption and to identify the factors that are likely to influence men's cosmetic consumption behavior utilizing data collected from Turkish males. Results indicate that self-esteem, lifestyle, societal beliefs, shopping, and self-image are critical determinants of men's cosmetic consumption. Findings further suggest that cosmetic shopping behavior of men is linked to self-image and lifestyle. Furthermore, the significant relationship between self-esteem and self-image, and between societal beliefs and lifestyle come to the fore. The paper ends with implications for the marketers and theoretical contributions to the growing research on gender differences.

Conceptual Framework and Research Hypotheses

Consumer behavior is the study of the processes involved when an individual selects, purchases, uses or disposes of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy needs and desires (Solomon, 1998). The present study aims at examining the Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel reference to the consumer at Tiruchirappalli City.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the impact of Television advertisements on the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel.
- To study the decision making on the basis of TV advertisements.

Hypotheses

1. There is an Impact of Television Advertising towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel
2. There is the relationship among the television advertising that helps towards the Selection of Branded Women's Apparel .

Materials and Methods

To meet the said objectives, descriptive study is chosen for research design. This includes a literature survey and primary data collection using questionnaire based on the literature review. For descriptive phase, A Cross-sectional survey of respondents was done using a structured questionnaire. Data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. A primary source of data collection is through questionnaires whereas secondary sources were journals, newspapers, national and international publications, internet, personal books, and libraries.

Sample Size

Data were collected on the basis of judgmental sampling. 125 respondents were given questionnaire and 100 were found to be fully usable for analysis. The sample size for the questionnaire was 100. A questionnaire was pilot-tested on a sample of 15 to ensure the validity of the survey instrument. However, post-elimination of incomplete responses, unreturned questionnaire and invalid answers, the final sample size used for analysis was 100.

The sample for the questionnaire was collected from consumers in Trichirapalli City.

Sampling Technique

Judgmental sampling was used. An initial set of respondents were selected on the basis of judgmental sampling. Subsequently, additional units were obtained on the basis of information given by initial sample units and then further referrals were taken from those selected in the sample. In this way, the sample was grown by adding more and more referral-based respondents until it reached the limiting number.

Judgmental Sampling was Based on the Following Parameters

- The sample comprised of people who Purchase apparel after seeing the television advertising.
- The sample comprised of people who spends the time to analyze a product for their purchase.

Statistical Tool

IBM SPSS Statistic version 20.0 was used for analysis. Cronbach's alpha test was used for checking the reliability of the data which is collected. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test for sampling adequacy and Barlett's test for sphericity is done. Factor analysis is done to identify the dimensions that act as the base for several variables which were collected. There may be one or more factors based on the nature of the study and total variables included in the study. Varimax rotation is used in factor analysis in order to produce factors that are characterized by large loading on relatively few variables. Multiple regressions are used in the analysis since there are more independent variables and one dependent variable. Descriptive study is chosen for research design. This includes a literature survey and primary data collection using questionnaire based on the literature review. Data were collected on the basis of random sampling (judgmental sampling). 125 respondents were given questionnaire and 100 were found to be fully usable for analysis. The questionnaire had questions based on various components of television advertising and Likert 5 scale rating was given for customers to rate their experience towards television advertising. The Chi-square goodness of fit test uses frequency data from a sample to test the hypothesis about a population proportion.

Statistical Tools Used

Using IBM SPSS Statistic version 20.0 the following tools were administered in this study 1) Reliability Test 2) Factor Analysis and 3) Multiple Regression 4) The Chi-square goodness of fit test.

Reliability Test

To check the reliability and consistency of the data, reliability test has been made and the obtained coefficient alpha value (Cronbach's alpha) was 0.815, and data has satisfactory reliability. Cronbach's alpha value above 0.5 can be used as a reasonable value for reliability.

Table Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.815	48

Factor Analysis

Table KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.614
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1.6923
	Df	780
	Sig.	.000

Inference

KMO test is to analyze the appropriateness of factor analysis. Values between 0.5 and 1.0 show that the factor analysis is appropriate and the value obtained was 0.614 which shows that the Kaiser – Meyer – Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is appropriate. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is to examine the hypothesis by correlation of variables in Chi-Square and correlation matrix of determinants. A value obtained in Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Chi-Square is 1.6923. This shows that all the statements were correlated and factor analysis is appropriate for the study.

Rotated Component Matrix

	Component												
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Colorful picture of TV Add's enables to make a purchase easier											.647		
Model/celebrities play an important role in enhancing a product													
Songs/lyrics help to position a product in the minds of a consumer													

Sound/music help to view the add repeatedly																				
Visualization displays the original characteristics of the product				.799																
Slogans add value to the advertisement.										.872										
Dialogues create an impact while making an apparel purchase.																				
Designs and Fashion of the apparel product help to make purchase decisions easy.																				
Brand Name of the Apparel products are made popular through Television advertisements								.792												
The advertisement gives Information to consumers.																				
Creative / Innovative advertisement reaches the consumer faster.				.722																
Duration of the advertisement has an impact on viewing the advertisement.																				
A message of the advertisement helps in communicating information to the customer.																				
Apparel Television Advertisement helps me in Immediate Purchasing.																				
Desire To Purchase is often created by Apparel Television Advertisement																				
Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement							.757													
Apparel Television Advertisement helps to avoid Dissatisfaction of products													.782							
Apparel Television Advertisement helps me to save time in purchasing																				
Mislead of the products by the retailer can be avoided through Apparel Television Advertisements																		.821		
Advertisement Recall is possible through Apparel Television Advertisement																				
Apparel Television Advertisement creates Interest to Watch Again.																				
Apparel Television Advertisement helps me to Recommend Others to purchase the products																				

Television advertisement creates a lifestyles segment, particularly among women towards Apparel Products								.801					
Television advertisement reveals more images of individualism that are especially appealing to the women for Apparel Products		.804											

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization. a. Rotation converged in 14 iterations

is Principle Component Analysis, where the total variance in the data is considered to determine the minimum number of factors that will account for maximum variance of data.

The factors are

- **Factor 1:** Due to TV ad exposure, I have started experimenting with new Apparel products.
- **Factor 2:** Television advertisement reveals more images of individualism that are especially appealing to the women for Apparel Products.
- **Factor 3:** Creative / Innovative advertisement reaches the consumer faster.
- **Factor 4:** Visualization displays the original characteristics of the product.
- **Factor 5:** Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement.
- **Factor 6:** Brand Name of the Apparel products are made popular through Television advertisements
- **Factor 7:** Television advertisement creates a lifestyles segment, particularly among women towards Apparel Products.
- **Factor 8:** Slogans add value to the advertisement.
- **Factor 9:** I mostly purchase Apparel products shown in TV ads
- **Factor 10:** Apparel Television Advertisement helps to avoid Dissatisfaction of products.
- **Factor 11:** Colorful picture of TV Add’s enables to make a purchase easier
- **Factor 12:** Mislead of the products by the retailer can be avoided through Apparel Television Advertisements
- **Factor 13:** TV ads make the purchase of the Apparel products easier

Multiple Regression

Hypotheses 1

1. There is an impact of television advertising on the Selection of branded apparel retail store.

Table Model Summary (b)

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	StdError of the Estimate
1	.789a	.547	.548	.709

- a. Predictors: (Constant), TV ads make the purchase of the Apparel products easier, Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement, Creative / Innovative advertisement reaches the consumer faster., Visualization displays the original characteristics of the product, Slogans add value to the advertisement., Mislead of the products by the retailer can be avoided through Apparel Television Advertisements., I mostly purchase Apparel products shown in TV ads, Brand Name of the Apparel products are made popular through Television advertisements, Television advertisement reveals more images of individualism that are especially appealing to the women for Apparel Products, Television advertisement creates a lifestyles segment, particularly among women towards Apparel Products, Colorful picture of TV ADD enables to make a purchase easier, Due to TV ad exposure, I have started experimenting with new Apparel products, Apparel Television Advertisement helps me in Immediate Purchasing.

Inference

Thirteen values represent the total variance explained by each factor. Percentage of the total variance attributed to each factor. One of the popular methods used in exploratory factor analysis

Inference

The model summary shows the R-value as 0.789 and this is the percentage variation in the overall impact of television advertising towards the Selection of branded apparel retail store.

Table ANOVA (b)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	22.927	13	1.764	3.512	.000a
	Residual	43.183	86	.502		
	Total	66.110	99			

a. Predictors: (Constant), TV ads make the purchase of the Apparel products easier, Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement, Creative / Innovative advertisement reaches the consumer faster., Visualization displays the original characteristics of the product, Slogans add value to the advertisement., Mislead of the products by the retailer can be avoided through Apparel Television Advertisements., I mostly purchase Apparel products shown in TV ads, Brand Name of the Apparel products are made popular through Television advertisements, Television advertisement reveals more images of individualism that

are especially appealing to the women for Apparel Products, Television advertisement creates a lifestyles segment, particularly among women towards Apparel Products, Colorful picture of TV ADD enables to make a purchase easier, Due to TV ad exposure, I have started experimenting with new Apparel products, Apparel Television Advertisement helps me in Immediate Purchasing.

b. Dependent Variable: Overall impact of television advertising towards the selection of branded women apparel is high

Inference

The above ANOVA table gives the F value to find the dependent variables associated with the Independent variables, the larger the F value more the variances. The F-ratio given under column F is 13.370 and p-value, 0.000 is given under sig. column. Since the p-value is less than 0.01, it implies that the calculated regression coefficient is significant and the variance in the independent variable contributes to the change independent variable. Therefore, it is inferred that the variance in predictors (Constant variable), really contribute to the factors that have the overall impact of television advertising towards the Selection of branded apparel retail store. (Dependent Variable).

Table Coefficients (a)

a. Dependent Variable: Overall impact of television advertising towards the selection of branded women apparel is high

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.260	.429		.605	.547
	Due to TV ad exposure, I have started experimenting with new Apparel products	.198	.077	.257	2.566	.012
	Television advertisement reveals more images of individualism that are especially appealing to the women for Apparel Products	.165	.086	.189	1.918	0.58
	Creative / Innovative advertisement reaches the consumer faster.	.142	.075	.181	1.890	.062
	Visualization displays the original characteristics of the product	.009	.072	.012	.126	.900

Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement	-.002	.083	-.002	-.021	.983
Brand Name of the Apparel products are made popular through Television advertisements	.129	.071	.172	1.824	.072
Television advertisement creates a lifestyles segment, particularly among women towards Apparel Products	.091	.069	.129	1.314	.192
Slogans add value to the advertisement.	-.036	.071	-0.48	-.505	.615
I mostly purchase Apparel products shown in TV ads	-0.75	.076	-0.97	-.990	.325
Apparel Television Advertisement helps me in Immediate Purchasing.	.026	.106	.027	.244	.808
Colorful picture of TV ADD enables to make a purchase easier	0.26	.084	.032	.316	.753
Mislead of the products by the retailer can be avoided through Apparel Television Advertisements.	.171	.072	.219	2.391	.019
TV ads make the purchase of the Apparel products easier	-.008	.081	-.010	-.104	.917

Inference

From the above table it is inferred that the value given under the column B against Constant is the a-value (0.260) and against Switch Over from old Retailer is possible by Apparel Television Advertisement is the b-value (0.983). Therefore regression is formulated as

$$Y = 0.260 + 0.983X_1$$

Chi-Square Tests

Chisquare indicate the relationship between the dependent and the independent variables.

H0 (null hypothesis): There is no relationship between the overall impact of television advertising on the selection of branded apparel retail store and the age factor.

H1 (alternative hypothesis): There is the relationship between the overall impact of television advertising on the selection of branded apparel retail store and the age factor

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	46.685a	9	.000

Likelihood Ratio	35.804	9	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.156	1	.142
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 8 cells (50.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .88.

Inference

From the above table, it is inferred that for 9 degrees of freedom the p-value is 0.000 is lesser than 0.05. The difference is considered significant. Since the Chi-square value is significant it means that alternate hypothesis is accepted and therefore there is a significant association between the overall impact of television advertising towards the selection of branded apparel retail store and the age factor.

Correlations

Correlation between Dimensions related to the impact of television advertising towards the selection of branded apparel retail store

Correlations					
		Attraction in Apparel Television advertisement	The effectiveness of Apparel Television Advertisement	Impact of Apparel Television Advertising	Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women
Attraction in Apparel Television advertisement	Pearson Correlation	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	100			
The effectiveness of Apparel Television Advertisement	Pearson Correlation	.186	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.063			
	N	100			
Impact of Apparel Television Advertising	Pearson Correlation	.366**	.437**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		
	N	100	100	100	
Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women	Pearson Correlation	.343**	.535**	.712**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	100	100	100	100

Inference

Correlation Interpretation

The above correlation table shows the intercorrelation between the dimensions - Attraction in Apparel Television advertisement, Effectiveness of Apparel Television Advertisement, Impact of Apparel Television Advertising, Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women,

Factors Having Positive Correlation at 1% Level of Significance

Comparatively high-level positive correlation at 1% level of significance among the variables exists between Attraction in Apparel Television advertisement and Impact of Apparel Television Advertising with a Pearson value of 0.366, then between Attraction in Apparel Television

advertisement and Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women with a Pearson value of 0.343, then between Effectiveness of Apparel Television Advertisement and Impact of Apparel Television Advertising with a Pearson value of 0.437, then between Effectiveness of Apparel Television Advertisement and Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women with a Pearson value of 0.535, then between Impact of Apparel Television Advertising and Gratifications of Apparel Television Advertising among Indian Women with a Pearson value of 0.712.

Conclusion

It has been inferred that T.V. advertising has an incredible impact on the purchasing behavior of ladies customers. Prior to buying any item customers/

buyers gather data for their appropriate obtaining basic leadership initiates consequently Advertising is generally embraced to get data about any items. There are diverse elements impacted on purchasing behavior of ladies customers in that it has been discovered that Social and individual elements have more affected. Greatest ladies shoppers affected by overhearing people's conversations in Trichy city. Along these lines, Television advertising assumes an essential job in purchasing behavior of ladies' buyer in Trichy city.

Scope For Further Research

This Study was finished by considering just a couple of factors. Additionally, research can be led by considering the all very much enjoyed measurements that influence the customer purchasing behavior. This investigation was directed just on Trichy City. Additionally, the study should be possible by including all the more testing edge at a national or universal level.

Limitations of the Study

Although the objective of the study is met, still there are some limitations to the present study.

- Firstly, the study conducted is limited to Consumers of Trichirappalli city.
- Secondly, only a few numbers of variables are selected for the study.
- Finally, the results are subject to a common limitation of the accuracy of the response.

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